

Shaping Cryptoeconomics as a New Market through Business Model Innovation

1 Conceptual Framework - Theoretical extended discussion

2 1.1 Business Definition

3 In addition to sensing and responding to changes in established markets, firms increasingly undertake
4 market shaping strategies to create new business opportunities (Nenonen et al., 2019; Gavetti et al.,
5 2017). In this regard, market systems are plastic and differ in their capacity to change (take form)
6 and to remain stable (retain form) during different points of time (Nenonen et al., 2014). According
7 to Nenonen and Storbacka (2018b), market shaping begins with re-focusing the Business Definition,
8 which also acts as a frame on the market that helps i) to comprehend the reality of the market system
9 as well as ii) perceive possible paths to start with. In their proposed Fan Framework, the Business
10 Definition represents a core layer, being a designable element itself through which the company sees
11 the rest of the layers. As demonstrated in Figure 1, the Business Definition “is part of the market”
12 and denotes two major answers: a position report (“element of *today*”) that mirrors firm’s identity,
13 as well as an aspiration or direction in which the firm is heading (“element of *tomorrow*”) (Nenonen
14 and Storbacka, 2018b).

Figure 1: Business definition

15 As one can notice, the Business Definition encompasses not only set actual and intended identity,

16 but it also addresses more clearly how the company see the market, by filtering and interpreting
17 it towards a new shape that would benefit it (Nenonen and Storbacka, 2018b). This exercise of
18 optimizing and framing the business definition enables the firm to embark on market shaping process
19 consistent with the conception that business modeling process is not linear (Mason and Spring,
20 2011). In this way, BM theory contributes to market shaping by offering a framework that may
21 help frame a purpose-oriented action (Latour, 2005; Mason and Palo, 2012) given its performative
22 nature of framing the way how the business (and the market) is developed and grown (Doganova
23 and Eyquem-Renault, 2009). As clarified by Mason and Spring (2011), a BM framework offers an
24 analytical perspective through which managers can seek to make sense of and share understanding
25 between individuals, groups, and organizations of what the situation is, becoming a constituent part
26 of what the market and what the firm is and does. Therefore, this market shaping strategy takes
27 under consideration that a focal firm performs various activities in the effort to shape a market
28 (Araujo, 2007) that can take place and have their effect at different levels of influence (Kindström
29 et al., 2018), which we present ahead as Technology, Market Offer, and System.

30 **1.2 Technology Level**

31 As highlighted by Teece (2010), in order to achieve a competitive advantage, technological innovation
32 often goes along with BMI, which may also lead to the creation of a new industry. Consequently,
33 technology fulfills a preponderant role as a functional base for the shaping of single and composite
34 activities, and the creation of useful market offers (Kindström et al., 2018). Technology is often the
35 key enabler behind new markets, and it is quite often the source of new potential markets (Sissons
36 and Thompson, 2012). To this end, it has been emphasized the close relationship between knowledge
37 and technology towards a perspective in which both physical and social things can be perceived as
38 embedded knowledge (Callon, 1998; Harrison and Kjellberg, 2016).

39 Consistent with the multifaceted nature of the Cryptoeconomics and, in particular, following
40 multiple conceptual, empirical, and market reports (Clayton, 2017; Lux and Mathys, 2018; Braddick
41 et al., 2018; Lux and Mathys, 2018; Braddick et al., 2018; Carrière, 2019; Basel, 2019; Blandin
42 et al., 2019), we identified three major elements (blockchain, mechanism design, and token offering)
43 from which could emerge a set of technology practices able to be exploited as drivers to create value
44 and foster BMI. These elements underpin the workings of the Cryptoeconomics market and need
45 to be available, viable, and compatible with the wider infrastructure and institutions (Sissons and
46 Thompson, 2012). However, (Lumineau et al., 2020) argue that blockchains offer a way to enforce
47 agreements and achieve cooperation and coordination that is distinct from both traditional contractual
48 and relational governance as well as from other information technology solutions. Therefore, we
49 posit these elements as subordinated to what Pelt et al. (2021) define as blockchain governance, that
50 is a “means of achieving the direction, control, and coordination of stakeholders within the context
51 of a given blockchain project to which they jointly contribute”.

52 Furthermore, the blockchain, mechanism design, and token offering are embedded with to what
53 Mason and Spring (2011) conceptualize as classes of technology, that is: core, product, process, and
54 infrastructure. Those elements are intrinsically inter-related, given that the decision for a specific
55 type of token demands a different type of blockchain with a given strategy for mechanism design,
56 including its governance model. As a social-material network embedded by the ‘object agency’
57 (Latour, 2005; Pace et al., 2017), these decisions encompass various market devices with almost the
58 same level of importance as individuals, such as mobile applications, web pages, e-wallets, smart
59 contracts, source codes, and databases.

60 For example, the Ethereum platform (currently the second-largest cryptocurrency project in
61 terms of market capitalization (CoinMarketCap, 2021)) has recently updated its consensus algorithm,
62 becoming based on Proof-of-Stake instead of Proof-of-Work. This public programme of action

63 producing clear and consistent rules of conduct forges the normalizing practices (Kjellberg and
 64 Helgesson, 2007b). On the other hand, adopting the Proof-of-Stake is clearly influenced by a
 65 technical image market representation pursued by the Ethereum community, whose expect less
 66 consumption of electricity, reduced centralization risks, and security against different types of attacks
 67 (Buterin et al., 2013). Since these activities depict how the market should work (Kjellberg et al.,
 68 2012), we may assume them as illustrative as illustrative examples of representational practices.

69 Most importantly, framing all these elements at Technology Level impacts further BM config-
 70 urations, including the Market Offer and System levels. This perspective reveals a commitment
 71 for the focal firm when acting in and perceiving a market and, consequently, to what was previous
 72 established as Business Definition (Nenonen and Storbacka, 2018b). In line with the previous
 73 arguments, we summarize in Figure 2 designable elements that can be managed or shaped by a
 74 firm in the Technology Level, in which goes beyond defining the Cryptoeconomics strategy *per*
 75 *se*. As claimed by Birkinshaw et al. (2008), technology elements should not be treated simply as
 76 ‘environmental variables’ but as part of the network of internal and external actors that practice the
 77 BM.

Figure 2: Technology level

TECHNOLOGY LEVEL		
References	Designable Elements	Conceptual Definition
Technology (MASON; SPRING, 2011)	Product Technology	Provide stable configurations of physical things
	Process Technologies	Organizational techniques that are used to buy components, make the product, and distribute them
	Core Technologies	Those that underlie particular product technologies
	Infrastructure Technologies	Those that enable connexions, including the internet, mobile networks and systems

78 Considering the organization is aware of how it will explore the Cryptoeconomics to frame

79 the market, including all the underlying technology that encompasses this configuration, we may
80 advance to the Market Offer level and approach further BM decisions related to the value proposition.

81 **1.3 Market Offer Level**

82 The market offer is intrinsically related to elaborating what should be exchanged, specifically that
83 the different market actors in a collaborative process need to define that object and the potential
84 value it might have (Finch and Acha, 2008). Following Massa and Tucci (2013) and the findings
85 from our SLR, we posit that this definition emerges as the product of two distinct pathways,
86 respectively defined as BMD and BMR. The BMD allows companies to commercialize new ideas
87 and technologies. The focus is on the entrepreneurial activity of creating, developing, and validating
88 a BM for a newly formed organization. Alternatively, BMR refers to the phenomena by which
89 managers reconfigure organizational resources to change a BM, that is, firms can also view the BM
90 as a source of innovation itself. This perspective is aligned to the view proposed by Nenonen et al.
91 (2019), in which market shaping can be used to create completely new market systems as well as to
92 improve existing market systems. Thus, both BMD or BMR are shaped according to the Business
93 Definition and market practices driven by the Technology Level from which denote how buyers and
94 sellers organize market activities and, consequently, how to facilitate interactions centered on the
95 exchange object (Ulkuniemi et al., 2015).

96 As we can notice, market offering concerns the nature of the producer-user interaction, rather than
97 any essential feature of a particular product or service (Normann, 2001). These service provision
98 efforts, also called exchange practices, gather what might seem to be the most straightforward
99 of market practices; it refers to the concrete activities related to the consummation of individual
100 economic exchanges (Kjellberg and Helgesson, 2007b). This includes all the idiosyncratic activities
101 related to a specific economic exchange, such as specifying and presenting products, negotiating

102 prices and terms of delivery, to mention just a few (Kjellberg and Helgesson, 2007a; Hankansson,
103 1982). In other words, the firm must decide exactly what product or service it is offering and agree
104 on a pricing logic, which means, as stated by Nenonen and Storbacka (2018b), more than just “how
105 much”. On this subject, Finch and Acha (2008) urge the importance of defining what should be
106 exchanged, specifically that the different market actors in a collaborative process need to define
107 that object and the potential value it might have. Hence, a market shaping strategy also involves a
108 method of connecting sellers and buyers, demanding an interaction between actors in a market or a
109 channel within it as a value proposition emerges (Kindström et al., 2018).

110 As clarified by Osterwalder and Pigneur (2010), the value proposition is described as an
111 aggregation of benefits, in the form of products or services, offered by a firm to its customers. To
112 drive future efforts of value proposition, firms have to assess their business architecture in terms
113 of value creation, value delivery, and value capture (Foss and Saebi, 2018; Teece, 2010). In this
114 sense, Lepak et al. (2007) point out that value creation depends on the relative amount of value
115 that is subjectively realized by a target user and that this subjective value realization must translate
116 into the user’s willingness to exchange a monetary amount for the value received. In summary, the
117 aim of market shaping is to enhance the value creation and realization for stakeholders in a market
118 (Nenonen et al., 2019). In turn, the concept of value delivery is mainly addressed as the process of
119 the floating value in a value network (Daeyoung and Jaeyoung, 2015). Further, value capture is the
120 realization of exchange value and is determined by the bargaining relationships between buyers and
121 sellers (Bowman and Ambrosini, 2000).

122 Then, relying on (Mason and Spring, 2011), we characterize the offering as consisting of the
123 value proposition opportunity arising from alternative combinations of artifacts, access to suppliers’
124 capabilities and capacities, and activities performed by the supplier(s) on the customer and/or its
125 property. By looking beyond the blinders of the seller-buyer duo, we overview in Figure 3 a list of

126 designable elements to the Market Offer level.

Figure 3: Marketing offer level

MARKET OFFER LEVEL		
References	Designable Elements	Conceptual Definition
Market Offering (MASON; SPRING, 2011)	Artefacts	Some tangible way of the product or service being consumed
	Access	Access to suppliers' capabilities and capacities
	Activities	Opportunities for differentiation and extra profit among firms used to an artefact-based offering
	Value	Benefits derived by a customer from an exchange
	Transactions	Occurs when a good or service is transferred across a technologically separable interface
	Relationships	Relationships between a focal firm and the organizations with which it transacts
Network Layer (NENONEN; STORBACKA, 2018a)	Infrastructure	What do customers need to use our products and services
Exchange Layer (NENONEN; STORBACKA, 2018a)	Sales item	What is being exchanged
	Pricing	How much is it worth
	Matching method	How do sellers and buyers find each other

127 By identifying a wide range of activities that companies and customers engage in the value
 128 proposition process, one can highlight the importance of interactions as well as the various
 129 roles of objects that lubricate market exchanges (Callon, 1998). For instance, in the context of
 130 cryptocurrencies, we may highlight the exchange practices around trading, payment, and selling
 131 activities, which are usually performed through mobile applications, web platforms, and e-wallets.
 132 These practices are of great importance since they are the most recognized by the general public
 133 and represent a direct point of contact with and between the users and sellers. As one can expect, a
 134 cryptocurrency exchange is not part of the regular stock exchange and face particular challenges, such
 135 as 24/7 operation and price volatility between exchanges. Hence, there is a number of cryptoexchange
 136 companies in the world competing, innovating, and aiming to improve the user experience as well as

137 easier the onboard of new customers to the market devices involved alongside the crypto trading
138 process.

139 **1.4 System Level**

140 Following Venkatesh et al. (2006), we address market as a set of institutions and actors located in
141 a physical or virtual space where marketing-related transactions and activities take place. Then,
142 markets pose as plastic and malleable systems in which are an outcome of actions by a network of
143 market actors (organizations and individuals) with interactions fostering value creation (Nenonen
144 and Storbacka, 2018a). As weighted by Kindström et al. (2018), “a narrow focus on the customer
145 is essential but not enough for shaping a market; instead, an understanding of the whole system,
146 including a focus on downstream actors, becomes important”. Viewed in this way, a market ecosystem
147 consists of a network of actors that goes beyond a firm’s immediate value chain, sometimes including
148 non-commercial players such as industry associations and public interest groups (Nenonen and
149 Storbacka, 2018b). These networks may be seen “as containers of knowledge and network relations
150 as conduits that convey knowledge from one place to another” (Russo-Spena and Mele, 2016).

151 In all this discussion of network architecture, the dynamic and evolutionary nature of BM
152 becomes clear by demonstrating that network connexions are not all about market transactions
153 (Mason and Spring, 2011). In the light of (Edvardsson et al., 2014), Kindström et al. (2018) advocate
154 that system level encompasses norms and regulations that set boundaries and rules for an entire
155 market. As institutionalized solutions, the markets are continuously formed and reformed through
156 the representational and normative practices in which actors engage to depict how they work and
157 how the organizations want to be seen (Kjellberg et al., 2015).

158 Market representations are arrangements of coherent but simplified illustrations of what a market
159 is and how it works (Nenonen et al., 2019). These image representations are used to symbolize the

160 market through elements like terminology, information such as statistics and media outputs, and
161 symbols such as industry events and awards (Nenonen and Storbacka, 2018b). It is worth noticing
162 that representational practices may change over time in response to the changing environment
163 supports, for example, market studies, sales statistics, media coverage, or academic work (Callero,
164 1994). In particular, the market of cryptocurrencies is widely influenced by representational
165 practices enacted through social media platforms (Beck et al., 2019). Businesses, developers,
166 investors, and even journalists covering the cryptocurrency media have been widely using social
167 media platforms to coordinate their efforts. Knowing this rich relationship, researchers have been
168 investigating cryptocurrency price valuation based on user comments (Kim et al., 2016) and social
169 media sentiment (Lamon et al., 2016), for instance. As one can see, central to representational
170 practices are ideas concerning *what* to measure and *how* to measure, that is, established measures
171 and methods of measurement which are respectively devised by normalizing practices (Kjellberg
172 and Helgesson, 2007b).

173 As we previously introduced, normalizing practices account for activities that contribute to
174 establishing guidelines for how a market should be (re)shaped or work according to some (group of)
175 actor(s), for example, standards, regulations, social norms, and guidelines on acceptable market
176 behavior (Kjellberg and Helgesson, 2007b). These activities on-going in all markets whereby formal
177 and social norms emerge or are consciously created (Nenonen et al., 2017). According to Sissons
178 and Thompson (2012), markets often depend on having established standards that all players can
179 follow to allow them to be coordinated and achieve critical mass. Nenonen and Storbacka (2018b)
180 state that such standards come about through lobbying and through power plays between key firms
181 identifying and targeting specific markets. According to them, this perspective has two important
182 implications for the practice of BM: i) the standards recognized by firms frame the way managers
183 identify and pursue market opportunities and ii) the notion of markets and standards might also

184 help managers frame practices for market-making as they seek to influence and shape standards in a
 185 strategic move.

186 Encompassing normalizing practices, for instance, some countries are reportedly planning to
 187 bring a law to ban cryptocurrencies, given that most ones are not backed by a public authority
 188 (Sapovadia, 2015). On the other hand, there are also governments currently working on the design
 189 of a prudential treatment for cryptoassets regulation (Blandin et al., 2019). In keeping with previous
 190 observations, we derived in Figure 4 a list of designable elements that the focal firm can try to
 191 manage or influence at the System Level.

Figure 4: System level

SYSTEM LEVEL		
References	Designable Elements	Conceptual Definition
Network Architecture (MASON; SPRING, 2011)	Market Standards	Come about through lobbying and through power plays between key firms identifying and targeting specific markets
	Capabilities	Institutional specialist know-how that is retained, maintained and developed by an organisation overtime
Network Layer (NENONEN; STORBACKA, 2018a)	Actors	Do we have the right actors in our network
	Rules & Know-how	Is work division optimal and does everyone know what they need toknow
Representation Layer (NENONEN; STORBACKA, 2018a)	Language	Naming, describing and familiarizing
	Information	Helping others to make sense of the market
	Symbols	Symbols to legitimize markets, including events, awards, and associations
Rules Layer (NENONEN; STORBACKA, 2018a)	Standards	Without them, nothing fits together
	Regulations	Defining what is legal
	Social norms	Making things acceptable and desirable

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